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RESULTS OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF ROTATOR CUFF INJURIES OF THE SHOULDER JOINT

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ABSTRACT

The causes of pain in the shoulder joint are most often associated with pathology of the subacromial space, reaching 70%. Rotator cuff injuries remain the most common pathology of the shoulder joint. Among the damages of the UMPS, small, medium, large and massive are distinguished, with the share of large and massive damage accounting for 56%. The study material was based on the data of 99 patients who underwent a bone-tendon anchor suture for a rupture of the umbilical cord between 2019 and 2023. There were 34 patients with grade 1 damage to the umbilical cord, 36 patients with grade 2 damage, and 29 patients with grade 3 damage. The results of the arthroscopic bone-tendon anchor suture were classified as “good,” “satisfactory,” or “poor” if they were confirmed in two or more rating systems. The use of arthroscopic methods for repairing rotator cuff injuries using anchors allows one to obtain good and satisfactory functional results. The reasons for the unsatisfactory results were the late referral of patients with massive injuries and fatty degeneration of the rotator cuff.

Keywords: rotator cuff, arthroscopy, bone-tendon anchor suture, bridging anchor suture

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РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ МАЛОИНВАЗИВНОГО ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПРИ ПОВРЕЖДЕНИЯХ ВРАЩАТЕЛЬНОЙ МАНЖЕТЫ ПЛЕЧЕВОГО СУСТАВА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Причины болей в области плечевого сустава наиболее часто связаны с патологией субакромиального пространства, достигающей 70%. Повреждения вращательной манжеты плечевого сустава (ВМПС) остаются самыми распространенными среди патологии плечевого сустава. Среди повреждений ВМПС выделяют малые, средние, большие и массивные, при этом на долю больших и массивных повреждений приходится 56%. Материалом исследования

были использованы данные 99 пациентов, которым был выполнен костно-сухожильный якорный шов разрыва ВМПС в период с 2019 по 2023 г. С повреждением ВМПС 1 степени 34 больных, со 2 степенью – 36 больных, 3 степени 29 больных. Результаты выполнения артроскопического костно-сухожильного якорного шва относили к категориям “хорошие”, “удовлетворительные” или “плохие”, если они подтверждались в двух и более системах оценки. Применение артроскопических способов восстановления повреждений вращающей манжеты плеча с применением анкерных фиксаторов позволяет получить хорошие и удовлетворительные функциональные результаты. Причинами неудовлетворительных результатов были позднее обращение больных с массивными повреждениями и жировой дистрофией вращательной манжеты плечевого сустава.

Ключевые слова: вращательная манжета плечевого сустава, артроскопия, костно-сухожильный якорный шов, мостовидный якорный шов

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YELKA BO‘G‘IMINING AYLANTIRUVCHI MANJETASINI JAROXATLARINI ZAMONAVIY JARROHLIK USULIDA DAVOLASH.

ANNOTATSIYA

Yelka bo‘g‘imidagi og‘riq sabablari ko‘pincha subakromial bo‘shliq patologiyasi bilan bog‘liq bo‘lib, 70% ga yetadi. Yelka bo‘g‘imining aylantiruvchi manjetining jaroxatlanishi (YeBAM) yelka bo‘g‘imi patologiyalari orasida eng keng tarqalgan patologiyalardan biridir. YeBAM jarohatlari orasida jaroxat o‘lchamigga qarab: kichik, o‘rta, katta va massiv jarohatlar ajralib turadi, katta va massiv jarohatlar esa 56% ni tashkil qiladi. Tadqiqot materialida 2019 yildan 2023 yilgacha bo‘lgan davrda YeBAM yorilgan suyak-pay ankerli fiksatsiyasidan o‘tgan 99 bemorning ma‘lumotlari keltirilgan. YeBAM 1-darajasi bilan 34 bemor, 2 daraja – 36 bemor, 3 daraja - 29 bemor. Artroskopik suyak-pay anker choklarining natijalari, ikki yoki undan ortiq baholash tizimlarida baholanib, uchta toifaga ("yaxshi", "qoniqarli" va "qoniqarsiz") ajratildi. Anker fiksatorlar yordamida yelkaning aylantiruvchi manjetining jarohatini tiklash uchun artroskopik usullardan foydalanish yaxshi va qoniqarli natijalar olish imkonini beradi. Qoniqarsiz natijalar YeBAM massiv jarohatlari va YeBAM mushaklarining yog‘li distrofiyasiga uchragan bemorlarda kuzatildi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Yelka bo‘g‘imining aylantiruvchi manjetasi, artroskopiya, Anker yordamida suyak-pay tikuvi, ko‘prik shaklidagi ankerli tikish.

Chronic pain and dysfunction in the shoulder joint associated with damage to the rotator cuff are the most common reason for seeking medical help among patients over 40 years of age (1,2,3,4). The current term “humeroscapular periathrosis” does not fully reflect the morphological essence of this problem.

The causes of pain in the shoulder joint are most often associated with pathology of the subacromial space, reaching 70%. Injuries to the rotator cuff (RCC) remain the most common among pathologies of the shoulder joint, reaching, according to the literature, 20.7% (5,6). Among the CMJ injuries, small, medium, large and massive are distinguished, with the share of large and massive injuries accounting for 56% (7).

As a rule, the development of large and massive injuries in elderly patients is preceded by an episode of low-energy trauma, or the injury is a degenerative process for which they, as a rule, do not seek medical attention. And only the appearance of severe pain along with a significant decrease in the function of the shoulder joint forces patients to seek medical help. Late treatment leads to atrophy of damaged UMJ tendons with subsequent fatty restructuring of muscle tissue. Such damage is often irreparable, and the number of recurrences after suture of the IMP can reach 20–90% (8).

The purpose of the study: Analyze arthroscopic treatment of rotator cuff injury and study the results of this pathology.

Research materials and methods. The research material was based on subjective examination data, preoperative radiographs and MRI of the shoulder joints of 99 patients who underwent a bone-tendon anchor suture for a rupture of the UMJ in the period from 2019 to 2023. 1st degree damage to the UMJ - 34 patients, 2nd degree - 36 patients, 3 degrees 29 patients. (diagram 1.)

Diagram 1.

The age of the operated patients ranged from 32 to 76 years (average age 56). There were 55 men, 44 women. In 62 cases, the intervention was performed on the right hand, in 37 cases - on the left hand. In 62 (62.6%) patients, the dominant upper limb was operated on. The follow-up period ranged from 1 to 2 years.

Criteria for inclusion of patients in the study: the presence of preoperative MRI signs of a complete rupture (full width rupture on oblique-sagittal tomograms) and massive rupture of the UMJ with retraction of the tendon edge of grades 1–3 according to D. Patte’s classification, muscular atrophy of grades 1–3 according to classification D. Goutallier in accordance with the data of preoperative MRI studies, as well as the presence of arthropathy of the shoulder joint (APS) no higher than stage 2 according to the K. Hamada classification. (Figure 1.)

Figure 1. Damage to the rotator cuff of the shoulder joint Patte: a - I degree, b - II degree, c - III degree

The criterion for exclusion from the study was the presence in patients of stages 3–5 APS on preoperative radiographs according to K. Hamada’s classification and grade 4 muscle atrophy according to D. Goutallier’s classification, as well as massive damage to the UMP with a combination of damage to the brachial plexus nerves.

Clinical methods. In the period from 1 year to 5 years after surgery, patients were surveyed and examined in the clinic with the completion of functional scales UCLA, ASES, CS. From the indicators characterizing the patient and reflecting the initial level of functional impairment, the following were selected: gender, age, presence of nicotine addiction in the patient, history of trauma or concomitant pathology (arterial hypertension, diabetes mellitus), duration of symptoms, period of observation of the patient, presence of preoperative stiffness (contracture) of the shoulder joint, presence of pseudoparalysis of the upper limb (LPLP), the initial severity of muscle atrophy of the UMPS according to preoperative MRI data. The following features of the treatment were taken into account: anchor suture technique (single-row or double-row bridge anchor suture), tenotomy or tenodesis of the long head of the biceps brachii tendon (LHB), arthroscopic subacromial decompression, shoulder joint redress before surgery or capsulotomy during surgery.

X-ray methods. All patients underwent preoperative standard radiography of the shoulder joint in direct and axial projections. The severity of APS was assessed using the K. Hamada classification [17]. Preoperative MRI was performed on a Siemens tomograph (South Korea) with a magnetic field strength of 1.5 Tesla, using a specialized Siemens matrix coil for the shoulder joint. The MRI technique included standardized examination protocols, which obtained T2 and PD-weighted fat-suppressed images in axial, oblique-sagittal and coronal projections.

Preoperative assessment of the degree of retraction of the tendon edge of the injured rotator cuff was carried out according to the D. Patte classification, the degree of fatty degeneration of the muscle part was assessed according to the D. Goutallier classification.

Surgical technique. All interventions were performed from four standard ports (posterior, anterior, posterolateral, anterolateral), as well as one or two additional mini-ports for the introduction of anchor fixators. After treating the footprint and the distal end of the ruptured tendon, anchors were inserted into the greater tuberosity of the humerus. Nodal anchors with a diameter of 5.5 mm with three threads (Threvo, Conmed) and Y-knot RC (Conmed) with three threads were used as anchors. Anchors made from polyetheretherketone (PEEK) were equally commonly used. In patients with grade 1 damage to the IMP according to Patte, a single-row anchor suture was performed. For patients with injuries of grades 2–3 of the IMPS according to Patte, a double-row bone-tendon anchor suture was performed. To fix the tendon edge, depending on the degree of its mobility and the configuration of the rupture, a single-row or double-row bridge-like anchor suture was used (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Arthroscopic picture of a rotator cuff injury: a – view from inside the joint, b,c – view from the subacromial space.

The rehabilitation protocol included a period of immobilization with a soft orthosis with a 45° abduction cushion for 6 weeks. Patients with damage to the 1st degree of UMPS according to Patte began passive development on the 2nd day after surgery, and the rest of the group of patients 2 weeks after surgery. And after 8 weeks, exercises involving the muscles of the shoulder girdle were allowed.

The results of arthroscopic bone-tendon anchor suture were classified as “good,” “fair,” or “poor” if they were confirmed in two or more rating systems. In accordance with the levels of indicators of the functional assessment scales ASES, CS and UCLA, groups of patients with good - 77 (77.7%), satisfactory - 20 (20.2%) and poor - 2 (2.02%) outcomes of the intervention were identified.

Additionally, the VAS scale was used to determine the nature of the pain syndrome and functional impairment.

At the time of examination of all 99 patients with ruptures of the UMJ after performing an arthroscopic bone-tendon anchor suture, the pain syndrome was completely absent in 82 (82.8%) patients, periodically bothered during physical activity in 15 (15.2%) patients, and persisted constantly (including including at rest, at night) in 2 (2%) patients. It should be noted that in 2 patients with poor outcomes, damage to the urinary tract was combined with adhesive capsulitis and impingement syndrome. In these patients, the pain spread along the outer surface of the shoulder, to the neck, collarbone, and scapula and was accompanied by an unstable decrease in the skin sensitivity of the fingers.

The degree of restoration of shoulder joint function was reflected in three scoring systems: CS, ASES, UCLA. The average indicators before surgery and at the time of examination were:

- for CS – 32.5±5.4 and 18.2±4.5 points;
- according to ASES 52.2±6.4 and 84.7±3.4 points;
- according to UCLA 18.2±1.8 and 26.4±34 points.

Based on the results of a postoperative MRI study, patients were divided into three subgroups depending on the degree of bone-tendon fusion of the IMP:

- A - with complete restoration of the tendon tissue of the rotator cuff;
- B — with partial restoration of the tendon tissue of the rotator cuff;
- C - with re-rupture or non-union of the reconstructed rotator cuff tissue. (table 1.)

Table 1.

	1 group (n=34)	2 group (n=36)	3 group (n=29)
Complete restoration of rotator cuff tendon tissue	32	27	16
Partial restoration of rotator cuff tendon tissue	2	9	11
Repeated tears or non-union of the reconstructed rotator cuff tissue	-	-	2

According to postoperative MRI studies, patients were divided into the following subgroups of patients: with complete (75 (75.8%) patients) or partial (22 (22.2%) patients) restoration of damaged rotator cuff tendons, as well as with re-rupture of the reconstructed tendon tissue (2 (2%) patients).

Conclusions: At the stage of preoperative planning in patients with rotator cuff injuries, it is advisable to measure the length and width of the expected tear, assess the degree of fatty degeneration of the muscle part of the rotator cuff elements on oblique-coronal and sagittal MRI scans in T2 mode to determine the type of injury geometry and prognosis of surgical treatment .

The use of arthroscopic methods for repairing rotator cuff injuries using anchors allows one to obtain good and satisfactory functional results. The reasons for the unsatisfactory results were the late referral of patients with massive damage and fatty degeneration of the urinary tract.

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